

Understanding Redox Kinetics of Iron-doped Manganese Oxides for High Temperature Thermochemical Energy Storage

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ABSTRACT

Thermochemical heat storage based on redox oxides has been proposed as suitable alternative for future concentrating solar plants working at high temperatures. In particular, the $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_2\text{O}_3/(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_3\text{O}_4$ redox couple is a promising system owing to its reduced cost, adequate thermodynamic characteristics and high stability over prolonged cycling. As demonstrated in this work, such redox materials can withstand over 75 reduction/oxidation (charge/discharge) chemical loops. The outstanding durability that this system exhibits has prompted a more comprehensive assessment of the kinetics of both charging and discharging reactions. The goal of this work has been twofold. First, based on data extracted from thermogravimetric analysis, we propose a rate law model for both reduction and oxidation reactions that could help to the future reactor design. Secondly, aided by *in situ* XRD and Raman spectroscopy we have gained further insight on the crystallographic transformations that take place during such redox processes and about the role of Fe incorporation on the oxidation improvement. Kinetic modelling results indicated that both reactions might be well described by a nucleation and growth mechanism. *In situ* XRD confirmed the presence of two spinel phases (cubic and tetragonal) in the reduced form. Finally, Raman spectroscopy analyses suggested that Fe incorporation alter the metal oxide bond lengths, namely, Fe doping induced an enlargement of Mn–O bonds. This structural modification facilitated their rupture and/or rearrangement, and it correlates well with a rise in oxidation rate with increasing the amount of Fe incorporated into the Mn oxide.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of reversible gas-solid reactions for storing part of the heat collected from the sun in concentrated solar power (CSP) plants has gained considerable attention since its implementation may solve the problems of intermittency associated with solar energy, allowing producing electricity round-the-clock¹. This technology, called Thermochemical Heat Storage (TCS), generally offers higher energy storage densities than systems based on latent or sensible heat². However, TCS systems are more complex and less mature so that research is still mainly at lab-scale. Of particular interest for future CSP plants working with volumetric air receivers is the use of high-temperature reduction-oxidation reactions of metal oxides. This is due to the fact that air can be used both as heat transfer fluid for the endothermic reduction of the oxide (charge) and as reactant for the exothermic oxidation of the reduced form of such oxide, process through which heat collected from the sun is released (discharge).

During the last years, BaO_2/BaO ^{3,4}, $\text{CuO}/\text{Cu}_2\text{O}$ ⁵, $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4/\text{CoO}$ ⁶⁻¹², $\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4$ ¹³⁻¹⁵, perovskite-based¹⁶⁻¹⁹ and Li-Mn spinels-based²⁰ systems have been suggested as promising redox couples for TCS. Research efforts have been focused on developing more efficient materials^{10,13,15,17}, novel TCS reactor concepts²¹⁻²³ or addressing the integration of such systems in a CSP plant^{12,24}. Two of the main problems associated with several of the aforementioned redox materials are the slow kinetics of the oxidation step and the degradation that many of these oxides suffered due to the high temperatures attained in the charge/discharge cycling process. Both chemical^{9,13-15} and morphological^{7,8,10,11} modifications have been explored as pathways for improving the kinetics and the chemical stability of such redox couples. Chemical modifications of Co- and Mn-based oxides have

been proved to remarkably increase their performance. In the case of the Co-based redox couple, Block et al. found that Cu/Co and Fe/Co mixed oxides presented higher energy storage densities and faster kinetics than the pure Co oxide¹⁵. However, those options are still more expensive than Mn-based oxides¹⁵, although those materials also show some limitations. Thus, besides presenting a lower energy density than Co-bases systems, the main drawback of the Mn₂O₃/Mn₃O₄ redox couple is the poor oxidation kinetics of Mn₃O₄^{15,25}. In this respect, we proved that oxidation rate of the Mn-based system could be greatly improved by incorporating Fe as to form a solid solution, which in turn increased the overall cycling stability^{13,14}. Namely, a material with 20 % Fe incorporation ((Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2})₂O₃) showed the fastest oxidation rates during several cycles if compared with Mn oxides with lower Fe concentration (Fe ≤ 10%) without any signal of deactivation over 30 cycles¹³. Furthermore that material presents higher energy storage density than Mn₂O₃/Mn₃O redox couple¹³ (254 kJ molO₂⁻¹ for (Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2})₂O₃ versus 195 kJ molO₂⁻¹ for Mn₂O₃²⁶). This system stores and releases heat through the following reversible reaction:

Reduction kinetics of un-doped Mn₂O₃ has been studied by few authors²⁷⁻³⁰, whereas oxidation of Mn₃O₄ has been evaluated just for TCS purposes by Pestalozzi³¹. This author found that oxidation kinetics should be most likely described by an Avrami-Erofeev model. However, to the best of our knowledge, a detailed kinetic analysis of neither the reduction of (Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2})₂O₃ nor the oxidation of (Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2})₃O₄ has been carried out yet. Due to the improved redox behavior of Fe-doped Mn oxides, a kinetic assessment of both processes could add more insight into the role of Fe incorporation, useful for further material improvement and for future reactor development. For instance, very recently Ströhle et al.

studied the best configuration for the integration of the Mn-based TCS system in CSP plants, using empirical rate laws for the reactor modelling.²⁴

In this work, reduction and oxidation kinetics of the $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_2\text{O}_3/(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_3\text{O}_4$ redox couple (Eq.1) have been analyzed for the first time by TGA and *in-situ* XRD. This last technique allows identifying the crystal phase transformation during both reactions using an X-ray diffractometer coupled with a high-temperature chamber. These *in situ* experiments have revealed the influence of the Fe loading (20% vs 1% Fe) on the crystallographic transformations and phase distribution. In addition, Raman spectroscopy analyses of these materials provided some hints on the role of Fe incorporation in the redox reactivity.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1. Materials preparation

$(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_2\text{O}_3$ was synthesized by a modification of Pechini method. Metal precursors, namely $\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (97 %, Sigma-Aldrich), and $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (>98 %, Sigma-Aldrich), were added to an aqueous solution of citric acid (CA, ≥ 99.5 %, Scharlab) with a Me:CA molar ratio of 1:5, with constant stirring for 3 h at 70 °C. Afterwards, ethylene glycol (EG, ≥ 99.5 %, Sigma Aldrich) was added with a molar ratio of CA:EG = 3:2 and kept during 2 h under stirring at 90 °C for gelification. Then, the gel was dried at 200 °C for 3 h and next calcined at 450 °C for 4 h in air. Finally, the calcined gel was ground to fine powders and further calcined at 700 °C for 4 h under static air, as to guarantee the formation of the bixbyite crystal structure. A sample with 1% Fe was synthesized using the same procedure and used for comparative purposes. A detailed physicochemical characterization of these two samples can be found in our previous work¹³.

2.2. Materials characterization

Raman spectra were recorded at room temperature using a JASCO NRS-5000/7000 series Raman spectrometer with the excitation source of 532 nm. Usually, data acquisition was performed with exposure time of 30 s and an accumulation value of 6. A SDT-Q600 TG-DSC equipment from TA instruments was employed for cyclability studies. In these runs, around 10 mg of material, placed in a 90 μ l alumina crucible, were subjected to 75 redox cycles. Each cycle comprised a heating step in which temperature was increased to 1050 $^{\circ}$ C, followed by a cooling step in which the sample temperature was lowered to 650 $^{\circ}$ C. Heating and cooling ramps were usually fixed to 10 $^{\circ}$ C min^{-1} , using a constant air flow (synthetic air 99.999 %, Praxair) of 100 ml min^{-1} for the entire cycling test. Simultaneously to TGA, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was carried out in order to study the heat effects during reduction and oxidation reactions. DSC was calibrated using the melting temperatures of several metals along the temperature range utilized for redox cycling.

2.3. Kinetic studies

A Netzsch STA 449 Jupiter F3 thermobalance was used for these studies. For these analyses ca. 10 mg of material were introduced in an alumina crucible (85 μ l) placed in a vertical ceramic sample holder. Such low amount of the oxide sample was used in order to avoid mass transfer limitations under the gas flow conditions established. Reduction kinetics was analyzed using dynamic experiments at different heating ramps ($\beta = 5, 10, 15$ and 20 $^{\circ}$ C min^{-1} , where $\beta = dT/dt$) under Ar atmosphere (Fig.S1). Dynamic runs were selected instead of isothermal ones in order to avoid the start of the reaction before reaching constant temperature. For oxidation kinetic studies, materials were firstly reduced by heating them up to 1000 $^{\circ}$ C under Ar atmosphere as to *in-situ* generate the reduced phase, which was

subsequently re-oxidized isothermally (Fig.S1) using an air flow of either 50 or 100 ml min⁻¹. Oxidation kinetics was analyzed with a furnace configuration that allowed passing the air flow downwards in order to enhance the contact between the gas and the solid. The gas inlet configuration has been proved to affect oxidation reactions of metal oxides when using a thermobalance.³² For that reason, the influence of using and upward or downward flow in the oxidation kinetic experiments was evaluated on a preliminary study. Fig.S2a shows that when the reacting gas came from the bottom, the reaction was much slower than in a down-flow configuration in which air came from the top. These results are in good agreement with those reported by Stamatiou et al.³². Thus, in order to avoid gas mass transfer limitations that could affect to the kinetic parameters determination, all the oxidation analyses were carried out with the down-flow configuration. Under these conditions, variations on the gas flow rate (Fig.S2b) or the sample mass (Fig.S2c) hardly affected the oxidation reaction.

2.4. In situ X-ray diffraction

A D8 Advance A25 powder diffractometer, equipped with an Anton Paar XRK 900 high temperature chamber, was employed for these assays. A fast response/high sensitivity detector Lynxeye XE was used. In situ X-ray diffraction (XRD) tests were performed using Gobel mirrors for Cu K α radiation (0.15405 nm wavelength) at a scanning rate of 0.1° s⁻¹ and with parallel geometry in the incident beam to avoid peak shift artifacts due to chemical or thermal expansion/contractions. Two types of *in situ* XRD measurements were carried out. Evaluation of oxidation reaction was performed under isothermal conditions. To this end, the starting material was firstly reduced in Ar heating it up to 900 °C for 1 hour. It was technically impossible to perform reduction in air, since temperatures higher than the operating limit for the Anton Paar XRK 900 chamber should be reached. Temperature was maintained at 900

°C during 1 h as to guarantee complete reduction. From that point, the sample was cooled down (in Ar) to the temperature at which oxidation was performed. At such moment air was injected to perform the oxidation during 1 h. Oxidation was studied varying the temperature from 850 to 600 °C. For reduction studies, Mn based materials were heated up to 900 °C at 10 °C min⁻¹ under Ar atmosphere. It should be mentioned that the intensity of XRD peaks was around 80 % lower when Ar was used as carrier gas instead of air due to an attenuation effect caused by the X-ray absorption of this gas.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. (Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2})₂O₃/(Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2})₃O₄ longevity test

As mentioned in the introduction, in our previous work we found that the Fe-Mn mixed oxide in the form (Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2})₂O₃ presented optimum characteristics to be employed as TCS material¹³. Namely, it showed fast and stable redox cycles over a 30 redox-cycle assay. In order to further corroborate the stability of such material, 75 cycles (Fig.1a) were carried out by TGA to such sample (20Fe). Fig.1b depicts the comparison of the weight signal for three representative cycles in more detail, indicating that this material could withstand prolonged cycling without deactivation. These results serve as a proof of concept about the feasibility of using this doped oxide for long term operation.

In parallel, the heat changes produced by the endo and exothermic reactions involved in this process were monitored by DSC. Fig. 1c compares the heat flow signal for the 2nd and 74th cycle. It could not be observed any significant difference between these two cycles, fact that also supports the high stability exhibited by this material. Fig.1d presents the cycling evolution of the oxidation enthalpy (energy released) with the number of cycles. The reduction enthalpy is not shown since accurate integration of the peak was not possible due

to the abrupt jump of the heat flow signal caused by the change from the heating to the cooling step. The oxidation enthalpy values experimentally obtained by integration of the DSC remained constant over the 75 cycles, with an average value of 171.1 kJ kg^{-1} . These values were lower than the ones we previously reported (same material, but using a different DSC equipment¹³), but in line with recent experimental results by Block et al. on a similar composition (Fig1d)¹⁵. These differences can be attributed to the substantial heat losses expected due to the use of open crucibles and the moderate heat conductivity of alumina, which are adequate for kinetic experiments but not ideal for thermochemical characterization. Nonetheless, the oxidation enthalpy values reported in this work are still higher than for the pure Mn oxides^{13,25}, confirming the beneficial effect of adding Fe on the TCS performance.

The high chemical stability observed for this material underlines the convenience of detailed analyses of both the reduction and the oxidation reactions involved in the charge and discharge steps, respectively. These results will be crucial for further reactor development and also could provide further insight in the role of Fe on the oxidation kinetic improvement.

Figure 1. (a) 75 redox cycles carried out to 20Fe material between 1050 and 650 °C, using heating and cooling ramps of 10 °C min⁻¹ under a constant air flow of 100 ml min⁻¹. (b) Comparison of the weight loss/gain for three representative cycles. (c) Comparison of the DSC signal for the 2nd and 74th cycle (exo up). (d) Oxidation enthalpy evolution with cycling for 20Fe sample, compared with other experimental and theoretical values found in literature.

3.2.Reduction kinetics

3.2.1. Reduction kinetic analysis by Friedman method

Gas-solid reactions can be described by an Arrhenius type law ³³:

$$r = \frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k(T)f(\alpha) = A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) f(\alpha) \quad (2)$$

where α is the conversion fraction, A the pre-exponential factor, E_a is the activation energy, R the gas constant, and $f(\alpha)$ the reaction model. The most representative models for solid-

sate reactions are shown on Table S1³⁴. The extent of reaction (α) can be obtained using several techniques³⁵, being the only requirement that the signal obtained can be used to estimate the conversion at a given time and temperature. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) is the most extensively used technique for analysis of gas-solid reactions, since it provides high quality data and allows avoiding in most cases external diffusion limitations. Based on thermogravimetric data of a reaction occurring with mass loss, α is obtained from Eq.3:

$$\alpha = \frac{m_0 - m_t}{m_0 - m_f} \quad (3)$$

where m_0 is initial weight, m_t is weight at time t and m_f is final weight.

Four runs at different heating ramps (β) were carried out as to extract kinetic data about the reduction reaction under Ar atmosphere (p_{O_2} approaching to zero). Reduction kinetic analyses were carried out under inert atmosphere as to reduce the operation temperature and to provide in this way the same experimental conditions used when analyzing the crystallographic transition via in situ XRD analyses (see section 2.4 for more details). It should be noted that performing these experiments under air ($p_{O_2} = 0.21$ atm) could have some kinetic implications as recently found by Varsano et al.²⁰. These authors reported abnormally large E_a values when the reduction of $LiMnO_2$ was carried out at $p_{O_2} = 0.2$ atm viz. up to one order of magnitude higher than those obtained under Ar atmosphere (1600 versus 425 kJ mol^{-1})²⁰. As stated by Varsano et al. when performing the kinetic analyses at relative high partial pressures of the gaseous product (e.g. O_2 release under air atmosphere) the effective activation energy is affected, among other factors, by the oxygen partial pressure²⁰. Hence, it is assumed that the same alteration of the E_a will occurred for the reaction evaluated in this work if reduction analyses will be performed under air atmosphere.

Fig.2 depicts the α -time plots of 20Fe ((Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2})₂O₃) reduction reaction. From these data it was possible to determine the E_a by applying the Friedman method³⁶ (Eq.4), which allows determining E_a without previous knowledge of $f(\alpha)$.

$$\ln\left(\beta \frac{d\alpha}{dT}\right) = \ln[Af(\alpha)] - \frac{E_a}{RT} \quad (4)$$

In this way, a plot of the left term of Eq.4 vs $1/T$ yields the E_a from the slope of the curve. According to Criado et al., this method gives more accurate values of E_a than Ozawa method³⁷. An example of an Arrhenius plots obtained by the Friedman method at $\alpha = 0.5$, from which E_a has been calculated, is displayed in Fig. 3. Regardless the degree of conversion applied, all these plots were linear, and the calculated activation energy exhibited quite stable values (Fig.S3) with an average value of 371.2 ± 18.7 kJ mol⁻¹. Table S2 collects the values of E_a and the correlation factors obtained from the Friedman method analyses.

Figure 2. α -time plots for reduction of 20Fe sample, carried out heating up to 900 °C under Ar atmosphere.

Figure 3. Friedman plot for the reduction of 20Fe sample at $\alpha = 0.5$.

For the reduction of un-doped Mn_2O_3 Botas et al. reported a value of E_a of $246.27 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ ²⁹. Accordingly, reduction of $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_2\text{O}_3$ requires more energy than reduction of pure Mn_2O_3 . This statement agrees well with our previous observations and is consistent with the higher onset temperature of this process¹³.

Once the E_a was determined, it was possible to analyze the reaction mechanism by applying the so-called master plots (Fig.S4, detailed information in Section S1, supporting information). Therefore, by introducing the average E_a value calculated through the Friedman method it will be possible to plot the experimental data in the master plots, which are depicted in Fig.4 showing the four runs conducted at different heating rates. At a glance, it can be observed that α -time plots in Fig.2 exhibited a sigmoid-shape that could be ascribed to nucleation and growth mechanisms. Master plot analyses confirmed this hypothesis, although some deviations from the theoretical curves were observed depending on the extent of reaction, making difficult to discern a pure mathematic model from these plots.

Interestingly, reduction seems to be well-described by A3 model during the first half of reaction, while at high conversions the experimental data tend to obey the A4 equation, and even in some cases it was not possible to clearly discern between such model and P2 (power law) one. Power law models also describe a nucleation and growth mechanism, although assuming a constant nuclei growth, being nucleation described by a power law³⁴. One possible reason for the model deviation observed at high conversions might be the presence of two phases in the reduced form of 20Fe sample¹³. This fact will be analyzed in more detailed in the next section via *in situ* XRD analyses. In general, a *n*th Avrami-Erofeev model seems to be the best descriptor for the reduction reaction of 20Fe sample. For pure Mn₂O₃ reduction, Francis et al. observed that the reaction was also described by an Avrami-Erofeev mechanism²⁸.

Figure 4. Master plot analyses for 20Fe reduction at (a) 5 °C min⁻¹, (b) 10 °C min⁻¹, (c) 15 °C min⁻¹ and (d) 20 °C min⁻¹.

On the other hand, Pestalozzi found that Avrami-Erofeev did not fit completely the experimental curve and, hence, applied the Sestak-Berggren (SB) model ³¹, which is an empirical model function as follows ³³,

$$f(\alpha) = \alpha^m(1 - \alpha)^n[-\ln(1 - \alpha)]^p \quad (5)$$

being m , n and p the kinetic exponents that better fit the experimental data.

SB empirical function was also applied in the present work as to obtain a more accurate equation describing such reaction. Fig.S5 depicts the SB fit in the differential form (Eq.5) for the experimental data taken from the TGA run performed at 20 °C min⁻¹. It can be observed that the SB function fits the experimental data when $m = 1.75$, $n = 0.7$ and $p = -0.75$. Thus, Eq.5 can be written as,

$$f(\alpha) = \alpha^{1.75}(1 - \alpha)^{0.7}[-\ln(1 - \alpha)]^{-0.75} \quad (6)$$

Once $f(\alpha)$ was determined, it was possible to calculate from the intercept of Eq.4 the last term of the so-called “kinetic triplet”, which is the pre-exponential factor A , resulting in an average value equal to $4.2 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ min}^{-1}$. Thus, the rate equation for $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_2\text{O}_3$ reduction under Ar atmosphere is,

$$r_{red} = 4.2 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ min}^{-1} \exp\left(\frac{371.2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}}{RT}\right) \alpha^{1.75}(1 - \alpha)^{0.7}[-\ln(1 - \alpha)]^{-0.75} \quad (7)$$

Due to its empirical nature, SB function has not an inherent physical meaning. However, in this particular case, 20Fe $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_2\text{O}_3$ reduction seems to follow a nucleation and growth

model. Owing to the sigmoidal shape of the α -time plots, the best fits in the master plots were those belonging to Avrami-Erofeev models (Fig.4). As mentioned above, results showed that the first half of the reaction could be described by A3 model and the last part by A4 one. The main physical difference between these two models is that A3 represents a two-dimensional nuclei growth, while A4 considers a three-dimensional one. In line with this, Avrami also stated that depending on the shape of the α -plots three types of growth were identified: linear, plate-like and polyhedral ³⁸.

Therefore, the overall $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_2\text{O}_3$ reduction can be described by a nucleation and growth mechanism, comprising the following steps: an induction period (nucleation), an acceleratory step (growth of nuclei) and a final deceleration (reaction completion). When a $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_2\text{O}_3$ particle is heated up to the reaction temperature, $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_3\text{O}_4$ nuclei appear first on the active sites located at the surface of the particles (the induction period). After this activation of nuclei on the reaction sites, nuclei grow on the surface and new nuclei must appear on the inside of the particle if heat is efficiently conducted from the surface to the bulk. The faster the heat transfer is, the quicker interior active sites reach the temperature at which reduction is thermodynamically favored and, consequently, the reaction rate is higher.

3.2.2. Crystallographic transformations during reduction reaction

Reduction of 20Fe sample was analyzed by *in situ* XRD performed in a high temperature chamber (more details in experimental section). This technique is a perfect complement to TGA, since it allows studying the crystal phase transitions that take place during the reaction. In our previous work we showed that, after reduction, 20Fe presented a mixture of both hausmannite and a minor contribution of cubic spinel β - $(\text{Mn,Fe})_3\text{O}_4$ ¹³. However, we also observed that for low Fe loadings ($\% \text{Fe} \geq 10$), materials exhibited just hausmannite structure

(tetragonal α -(Mn,Fe)₃O₄)¹³. In order to confirm this fact, the crystallographic transformations occurring during reduction of a sample with low Fe concentration, namely 1 % Fe, were also investigated for comparative purpose.

Fig.5 displays the 2D *in situ* X-ray diffractograms recorded to both samples in a temperature range from 700 to 900 °C in Ar atmosphere. Intensity of the X-ray peaks is described by the scale of color intensity depicted on the right bar. Fig.5 shows that reduction of 20Fe sample takes place at higher temperature than that of 1Fe. Interestingly, the reduced phases varied from those previously reported¹³, and in this case the principal crystal phase observed was cubic spinel, also known as jacobsite, with a minor contribution of tetragonal Mn₃O₄. Nevertheless, the present results agree better with those reported in Fe-Mn-O phase diagrams at such temperature and Fe content³⁹. Differences with previous reports could be due to the kinetic control of phase composition. For the sake of clarity, Fig.S6 depicts the XRD patterns taken at 900 °C to both 1Fe and 20Fe samples. In the case of 20Fe, the peaks attributed to the tetragonal Mn₃O₄ (hausmannite) suffered a shift due to the substitution of Mn²⁺ by Fe²⁺, which has slightly different ionic radius in fourfold coordination (0.66 and 0.63 Å, respectively⁴⁰). Therefore, for low Fe contents, the phase transition that occurs during reaction is from cubic (Mn,Fe)₂O₃ to tetragonal α -(Mn,Fe)₃O₄, whereas for 20Fe, bixbyite is mainly transformed into cubic β -(Mn,Fe)₃O₄ and, in a minor extent, into the tetragonal spinel, that is, into two polymorphic phases.

Another interesting feature observed for 20Fe sample in these temperature-resolved X-ray diffraction patterns, is the appearance of the tetragonal spinel (hausmannite, labeled as H) at lower temperatures than the cubic spinel (jacobsite, noted as J). The tetragonal phase showed stable intensity values between 800 and 900 °C, whereas the cubic spinel exhibited a fast

intensity increase at high temperatures ($> 850\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). This fact might justify the aforementioned model deviation at high conversions, observed in the Master Plots for 20Fe reduction (Fig.4) because it is suggested that each phase might follow a different nucleation and growth model. At low conversions, the formation of the tetragonal spinel (H) took place, with almost no presence of the cubic spinel. At high temperatures, when reaction was reaching high conversions ($\alpha > 0.5$), formation of the cubic spinel prevailed, which correlates well with the deviation from A3 model.

Figure 5. Contour plots of reduction reaction monitored using *in situ* XRD. Reaction was carried out under Ar flow of 100 ml min^{-1} . (H = tetragonal $(\text{Mn,Fe})_3\text{O}_4$; B = Mn_2O_3 and J = cubic $(\text{Mn,Fe})_3\text{O}_4$). The right bar indicates the peak intensity.

3.3.Oxidation kinetics

3.3.1. Oxidation kinetic analysis by isothermal method

Oxidation kinetic parameters were extracted from isothermal TGA runs. In each of these TGA runs reduction was previously conducted in Ar atmosphere as to *in-situ* generate the reduced phase, $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_3\text{O}_4$, which is the subject of this study. The α -time plots based on the isothermal experiments are depicted in Fig.6. From these results it was observed that $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_3\text{O}_4$ oxidation kinetics followed two different trends depending on the temperature at which the oxidation was carried out. From 650 to 725 °C the reaction followed an Arrhenius behavior, described by an increasing oxidation rate as the temperature was higher. The opposite result was attained from 725 to 800 °C, since in this range oxidation suffered a deceleration. Indeed, at 800 °C reaction did not achieve full conversion after 13 min, whereas at 725 °C the highest reaction rate was observed leading to a total conversion in just 8 min.

Once kinetic data (α, t) was extracted at different temperatures, it was possible to represent the experimental points in the master plots following the steps described in the Supporting Information. Unlike for reduction kinetics analysis carried out under dynamic conditions, by using isothermal experiments the reaction model can be inferred by applying the master plot method without previous knowledge of the E_a (See SI for more details). Fig.7 depicts the master plots in the integral form for $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_3\text{O}_4$ oxidation at temperatures from 650 to 725 °C. Results indicated that, regardless the temperature assayed, oxidation followed an Avrami-Erofeev mechanism. Namely, oxidation could be described by nucleation and two-dimensional growth of nuclei mechanism (A3). However, as in the case of the reduction reaction, at high conversions ($\alpha > 0.75$) experimental data deviate from such model, showing an intermediate behavior between A2 and A3 models.

Figure 6. α -time plots at (a) $T = 650$ - 725 °C and (b) $T = 725$ - 800 °C.

Figure 7. Master plot analyses for 20Fe oxidation at (a) 650 °C, (b) 675 °C, (c) 700 °C and (d) 725 °C.

As an attempt to find a more accurate descriptor for $f(\alpha)$, the SB empiric model was used to fit the oxidation data. Fig.S7 displays the results for the SB fit to the experimental data of the reaction carried out at 725 °C. Results shows that SB function described well the experimental data when $m = 1.26$, $n = 0.522$ and $p = -0.59$ were chosen as SB coefficients. Therefore, $f(\alpha)$ can be written as,

$$f(\alpha) = \alpha^{1.26}(1 - \alpha)^{0.522}[-\ln(1 - \alpha)]^{-0.59} \quad (8)$$

Re-arranging Eq.2 and taking natural logarithm in both sides, it is obtained,

$$\ln \left(\frac{d\alpha/dt}{f(\alpha)} \right) = \ln A - \frac{E_a}{RT} \quad (9)$$

Thus, once $f(\alpha)$ was determined, the kinetic parameters could be calculated from a representation of the left side of Eq.9 against the reciprocal of the temperature. From the slope E_a is obtained, and the intercept yields A . Fig.8 shows the Arrhenius plot for $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_3\text{O}_4$ oxidation under air and at $\alpha = 0.5$. It can be seen the two trends observed before in α -time plots. From 650 to 725 °C the reaction followed an Arrhenius behavior, in which oxidation rate increased with temperature, reaching the maximum rate at 725 °C. Further raising the temperature had the opposite effect, so the reaction rate decreased linearly. Several non-Arrhenius behavior cases have been reported in literature, especially in the case of kinetics of reversible gas-solid reactions at high temperature⁴¹⁻⁴⁴. Those authors observed that an increase of temperature in their assays caused a decrease in the backward reaction rate. For reversible redox reactions, the high-temperature oxidation deceleration has been mainly attributed to the influence of the reverse reaction^{3,43,44}. This is in agreement with the behavior observed for $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_3\text{O}_4$ oxidation in air. In the case of the reduction reaction studied in the previous section, the effect of the reverse reaction was avoided by carrying out the kinetic study under Ar atmosphere that is, preventing from any possible re-oxidation.

The deceleration of the rate observed at high temperatures added an interesting feature to the determination of E_a : at these high temperatures (from 725 to 800 °C) the curve presented a positive slope, which in turn gave a negative E_a . Negative E_a of other processes have been recently reported⁴². A negative value for the activation energy has no physical meaning in the frame of the “activated complex” model. Therefore, in the present work E_a was

determined only for the temperature range at which reaction followed an Arrhenius behavior, which yields a positive E_a .

Figure 8. Arrhenius plot for 20Fe oxidation at $\alpha = 0.5$. The black-dashed line shows the linear fit for the data following the Arrhenius behavior. Red-dashed line is the polynomial fit for all the points as visual guide of the overall tendency and it has no physical meaning. Activation energy was determined for several degrees of conversion, as depicted in Fig.S8. Results exhibited quite similar values, with correlation factors close to 0.99 in most of the cases (Table S2), resulting in an average E_a of 74 ± 7 kJ mol⁻¹. This value is one order of magnitude lower than for reduction reaction. Muroyama *et al.* obtained a similar result when analyzing the redox kinetics of the Co₃O₄/CoO system, indicating that lower E_a values for oxidation were due to a weaker dependence of oxidation with temperature.⁴⁵ Thus, the kinetic rate law for the oxidation reaction can be expressed by the following equation for temperatures lower than 725 °C,

$$r_{ox} = 2.3 \cdot 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1} \exp\left(\frac{74 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}}{RT}\right) \alpha^{1.26} (1 - \alpha)^{0.522} [-\ln(1 - \alpha)]^{-0.59} \quad (10)$$

3.3.2. Crystallographic transformations during oxidation reaction

It has been found that the mechanism that better describes the $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_3\text{O}_4$ oxidation is a nucleation and two-dimensional growth. In order to get further insight about the crystal transformations that take place during such process, the oxidation was analyzed via *in situ* XRD under air atmosphere. First, $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_2\text{O}_3$, was reduced in pure Ar up to 900 °C. Secondly, the sample was cooled down under Ar atmosphere as to avoid re-oxidation before the temperature reached constant values, time at which air was injected.

Fig.9a shows the time-resolved XRD evolution of $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_3\text{O}_4$ oxidation under air atmosphere at 700 °C. As mentioned before, this material exhibited a phase mixture in its reduced form, with cubic $(\text{Mn,Fe})_3\text{O}_4$ (jacobsite, J) as main phase, and tetragonal $(\text{Mn,Fe})_3\text{O}_4$ (hausmannite, H) in lower proportion. Both were transformed into cubic $(\text{Mn,Fe})_2\text{O}_3$ (bixbyite, B) under the presence of the oxygen contained in air. Comparing these results with those obtained in the thermogravimetric assays (Fig.6a) at the same temperature, it is evidenced that with the configuration of this experiment the reaction was slower. This is ascribed to factors related with the XRD reaction chamber and the sample configuration, since a remarkable higher quantity of mass was required for proper sample preparation, which was crucial to avoid measurement errors. It can be observed that on the first scans, the intensity of hausmannite and jacobsite reflections was quite stable. However, the first evidence of bixbyite phase was observed after 850 s of exposure to air, whereas jacobsite and hausmannite peak intensity started to decrease after 1100 s. This suggested that during a certain period of time bixbyite phase was growing but not at the expense of the disappearance of jacobsite and hausmannite. In order to evaluate this fact in more detail, oxidation was

analyzed through *in situ* XRD at 600 °C, since at this temperature reaction should be slower and, hence, peak evolution could be easier to monitor in detail.

Fig.9b displays the XRD evolution of $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_3\text{O}_4$ oxidation at 600 °C. As expected, the reaction was slower under these conditions, taking 2 h to reach almost full conversion. On Fig.9c the zone in which the first bixbyite peaks appeared is zoomed for the sake of clarity. There it can be appreciated in a clearer way that the peaks associated to the oxidized phase bixbyite (B) emerged without noticeable decrease on the existent reduced phases, neither jacobsite (J) nor hausmannite (H). Moreover, the peak intensity of B phase increased considerably, whereas those of J and H remained quite stable, and it was after 50 min when such peaks started their progressive intensity decrease.

The crystallographic transition for the oxidation reaction was also studied for the materials with low Fe content, as to corroborate the differences in the crystallographic transition and the reaction rate. In our previous work, we showed that oxidation was three times faster for 20Fe than for 1Fe¹³.

In order to check if this behavior was only present in 20Fe sample, Fig.10a depicts the *in situ* XRD patterns of 1Fe $(\text{Mn}_{0.99}\text{Fe}_{0.01})_3\text{O}_4$ during 2h oxidation under air atmosphere at 700 °C. In this case, the progressive growth of bixbyite phase while hausmannite concentration remained stable was even easier to observe, especially Fig.10b, in which the time-resolved XRD of 1Fe is zoomed for the sake of clarity. For 1Fe sample, 2 h were not enough to reach full oxidation. Reaction (bixbyite formation) started after 40 min at 700 °C. However, hausmannite peak intensity did not significantly decrease until ca. 80 min of treatment under oxidative atmosphere. Thus, regardless the amount of Fe, it seems that the transition between

the spinel $(\text{Mn,Fe})_3\text{O}_4$ and the bixbyite $(\text{Mn,Fe})_2\text{O}_3$ exhibited a peculiar transition. Fig.10c shows a comparison of three XRD patterns taken at three different times, representative of the reaction evolution. It can be observed that intensity of $(\text{Mn}_{0.99}\text{Fe}_{0.01})_3\text{O}_4$ reflections suffered a slight decrease if compared with how $(\text{Mn}_{0.99}\text{Fe}_{0.01})_2\text{O}_3$ peaks grew. In Fig.10b it was more difficult to appreciate such small decrease. At first sight, one might think that such anomalous behavior of the $(\text{Mn}_{0.99}\text{Fe}_{0.01})_2\text{O}_3$ material could be related with some additional crystallographic transformations, for instance, amorphous $(\text{Mn}_{0.99}\text{Fe}_{0.01})_3\text{O}_4$ being transformed into $(\text{Mn}_{0.99}\text{Fe}_{0.01})_2\text{O}_3$. However, it was found that a direct semi-quantitative correlation between peak intensities and concentrations of these two phases may be misleading if a correction for the reference intensity ratio (RIR) of each crystal phase is not applied. RIR method scales the diffraction data to a reference, which is normally corundum. Interestingly, RIR factors for hausmannite (Mn_3O_4) and bixbyite (Mn_2O_3) show a significant difference. Values found in the database of X'pert HighScore Plus software⁴⁶ are $\text{RIR}(\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4) = 2.54$ and $\text{RIR}(\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3) = 4.96$. This indicates that under the same conditions, Mn_2O_3 reflections tend to present a higher intensity than Mn_3O_4 ones. This fact might explain the anomalous growth observed for $(\text{Mn,Fe})_2\text{O}_3$ phase. In order to check that, the intensities of (013) reflection of $(\text{Mn}_{0.99}\text{Fe}_{0.01})_3\text{O}_4$ and (222) peak for $(\text{Mn}_{0.99}\text{Fe}_{0.01})_2\text{O}_3$ were corrected applying the aforementioned RIR factors. The time evolution of both values during the reaction carried out isothermally at 700 °C is plotted in Fig.11. It can be observed that by correcting the intensities with the RIR factor the formation of $(\text{Mn}_{0.99}\text{Fe}_{0.01})_2\text{O}_3$ is almost proportional to the decay of $(\text{Mn}_{0.99}\text{Fe}_{0.01})_3\text{O}_4$. Therefore, the peculiar appearance of $(\text{Mn,Fe})_2\text{O}_3$ phase observed in the time-resolved *in situ* XRD patterns was due to the different intensity ratios that each crystal phase presents and not to any atypical crystallographic transformation.

Figure 9. X-ray diffractograms recorded *in situ* during $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_3\text{O}_4$ oxidation under air atmosphere at (a) 700 °C and (b) 600 °C. For the sake of clarity XRD patterns recorded at 600 °C are zoomed in (c). (H = hausmannite, J = jacobsite and B = bixbyite).

Figure 10. (a) X-ray diffractograms recorded *in situ* during $(\text{Mn}_{0.99}\text{Fe}_{0.01})_3\text{O}_4$ oxidation under air atmosphere at 700°C . (H = hausmannite, and B = bixbyite). (b) Zoom of the red-dashed line. (c) Comparison of three diffractograms taken at different times.

Figure 11. Time evolution of the corrected intensity for the main peaks of $(\text{Mn,Fe})_3\text{O}_4$ and $(\text{Mn,Fe})_2\text{O}_3$ crystal phases for 1Fe sample.

3.3.3. Oxidation mechanism

Based on the results obtained through the kinetic modelling and the information extracted from *in situ* X-ray diffraction tests, a mechanism for this reaction can be established. Oxidation starts with the activation of nuclei sites on the particle surface which triggers the reaction. Nucleation sites can be imperfections such as defects, impurities, strains³⁴ or grain boundaries⁴⁷. This process must involve oxygen adsorption by the oxide surface and dissociation of molecular oxygen into oxygen anions. However, oxygen can be adsorbed and further dissociated into oxygen anions through different pathways. Several oxygen species can be found on oxide surfaces, such as O^- , O_2^- , O_2^{2-} ⁴⁸. In this case, it will be assumed the simplistic scenario, in which an oxygen molecule is adsorbed on the Fe-Mn oxide surface, and after electron transfer between the adsorbate and the Fe and Mn cations located on the

surface, O_2 is dissociated in oxygen anions O^{2-} . Then, oxygen anions are incorporated into the crystal, generating cation vacancies and electron holes⁴⁹.

The steps described until now are meant to be involved in the reaction start (induction period) by triggering the formation of incipient nuclei (germ nuclei). However, it should be kept in mind that oxygen is up-taken during the whole extent of the oxidation reaction, albeit at different rates given by the classical sigmoidal shape. The induction step will continue with the formation of the first nuclei. Normally in this type of oxides oxidation will imply a chemical diffusion performed by cations, since formation of oxygen vacancies is energetically unfavorable⁴⁹. Thus, cation vacancies are formed when oxygen is incorporated. $(Mn,Fe)_3O_4$ is a normal spinel, with cations occupying both tetrahedral and octahedral sites. Therefore, cationic vacancies can be generated at either tetrahedral or octahedral sites. In addition, cations and cationic vacancies can follow three different mechanisms for migration: hopping within octahedral sites, hopping within tetrahedral sites or between both sites⁴⁹. However, determining the actual mechanism of cationic (and vacancy) diffusion through the crystal lattice and how the bivalent cations are oxidized to trivalent cations with the consequent bond rearrangement is complex, and requires additional analytical techniques or DFT calculations⁵⁰. In any case, the aim of this section is to give a brief summary of the various steps that might be included in the formation of the first nuclei of $(Mn,Fe)_2O_3$. Once formed, the oxidation progresses by the growth of the formed nuclei, which is usually ascribed to the acceleratory zone of the sigmoidal α -time plots. Growth of nuclei generally takes place in two different ways: ingestion or coalescence³⁴. Ingestion implies the elimination of a potential active site, at which another nucleus could have been formed, by growth of existing nuclei over it. Coalescence (overlap of nuclei) is related with merging of two existing nuclei

giving rise to a larger nucleus. Reaction will progress with growth of nuclei in the acceleratory period until the oxidation reaction reaches a point of inflection at maximum rate. After this point, the $(\text{Mn,Fe})_3\text{O}_4$ particle has been almost totally transformed into $(\text{Mn,Fe})_2\text{O}_3$ (high conversion zone), thus the continued expansion of nuclei is no longer possible, reaching the reaction the deceleratory period, which eventually ends with the complete formation of $(\text{Mn,Fe})_2\text{O}_3$.

3.3.4. On the role of Fe in improving oxidation rate

As showed in our previous word, oxidation for 1Fe was much slower than for 20Fe¹³. This was also the case when analyzing the oxidation of both materials isothermally. In Fig.S9a it can be observed that at 675 °C, oxidation of 1Fe sample needed 110 min to reach full conversion, whereas for 20Fe sample just 13 min, corroborating the remarkable kinetic improvement caused by incorporation of Fe.

Fig.S.9b displays the master plot analysis performed to analyze the mathematic function that better describes the oxidation of 1Fe sample. It can be observed that such reaction fitted very well an A2 model, which is also an Avrami-Erofeev mechanism. A2 describes a reaction with random nucleation, whereas A4 proposes a three-dimensional nuclei growth^{51,52}. According to Rouet-Leduc et al., the Avrami exponent ($n = 2$ for A2, $n = 4$ for A4) can also serve to distinguish between homogenous and heterogeneous nucleation, being also these two paths related to the materials microstructure⁴⁷. Homogeneous nucleation tends to be spontaneous and takes place at random sites, whereas heterogeneous nucleation occurs at preferred sites, which usually are imperfections, grain boundaries or impurities. It seems that for the oxidation step, the reaction mechanism varies very little depending on the Fe loading,

making difficult to discern if the difference between homogenous and heterogeneous nucleation could have any implication on the kinetic improvement.

Raman spectroscopy was utilized in order to get information about the near-order structural differences between $(\text{Mn}_{0.99}\text{Fe}_{0.01})_3\text{O}_4$ (1Fe reduced phase) and $(\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})_3\text{O}_4$ (20Fe reduced phase) that might motivate the rate improvement of oxidation reaction. Fig.12 illustrates that 1Fe clearly exhibited the Raman modes associated with Mn_3O_4 (hausmannite). That is, an intense peak at 652 cm^{-1} , and two weak peaks at 313 and 369 cm^{-1} . According to Julien et al.⁵³ the peak at 652 cm^{-1} is ascribed to A_{1g} mode, related to Mn–O breathing vibration of Mn^{2+} cations in tetrahedral positions⁵³. It is assumed that those Mn^{2+} cations on the tetrahedral sites are the main species involved in the oxidation process, since in the bixbyite structure only Mn^{3+} and Fe^{3+} are expected. Thus, during oxidation, it is suggested that Mn^{2+} cations will probably experience: (a) migration to octahedral positions and (b) oxidation by neighboring oxygen anions. Fe cations contained in the spinel lattice might play an important role in these events, namely, the presence of Fe species in either tetrahedral or octahedral sites could facilitate bond rearranging during the oxidation process, which in turn could explain why incorporation of Fe into the spinel structure is remarkably improving the oxidation reaction.

Comparing the Raman spectra of 1Fe and 20Fe samples before oxidation, several differences were observed (Fig.12). The most important is that the main peak, the one at around 652 cm^{-1} , experienced a shift to lower wavenumbers when Fe content was increased to 20 mol %. Namely, such peak was displaced to 643 cm^{-1} . Weckhuysen and Wachs⁵⁴, found an inverse relation between the Raman frequency and the length of Cr–O bonds. Namely, a shift to lower frequencies implied an enlargement of the metal-oxide bond. Although these authors

found such relation for dispersed Cr oxides, a similar behavior could account for these Raman observations. Thus, it is suggested that the shift to lower frequencies caused by Fe incorporation is related with an enlargement of Mn–O bonds of Mn^{2+} cations located in tetrahedral positions. This could explain the influence of Fe at atomic level on enhancing oxidation rate. The hypothesis is based on the fact that longer Mn–O bonds will be easier to break and rearrange than shorter bonds. The presence of Fe, probably as Fe^{2+} in tetrahedral positions, might facilitate the mobility of Mn^{2+} cations owing to easier Mn–O rearrangement. Then, it is assumed that a faster Mn^{2+} cation migration to octahedral sites could influence the oxidation rate, eventually improving its kinetics. Although an easier mobility of cations seems a plausible reason for faster oxidation reaction, this hypothesis should be confirmed by other computational/experimental methods.

Figure 12. Raman spectra of 1Fe and 20Fe, after reduction in TGA up to 1000 °C under Ar atmosphere. Raman was recorded using 532 nm laser.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, reduction and oxidation kinetics were analyzed, trying to ascertain the mechanism of each process. Kinetic modelling has been employed in order to determine the rate law for each reaction, which in turn might be useful for further reactor development. Both oxidation and reduction reactions seem to follow nucleation and growth models, fairly-well described by Avrami-Erofeev mechanisms according to the kinetic analysis using master plots. However, due to the deviation of the experimental results from the model, especially at high conversions ($\alpha < 0.75$) the empiric Sestak-Berggren formula has been utilized in order to find a more accurate, but empirical, description for $f(\alpha)$. Activation energies were determined for both processes although oxidation shows a non-Arrhenius behavior for temperatures above 725 °C. Comprehensive mechanisms for both reduction and oxidation reactions were exposed, based on the results obtained from the kinetic modelling.

In situ XRD results reveal that during reduction of the oxides with low Fe content, the phase transformation is from cubic $(\text{Mn,Fe})_2\text{O}_3$ to tetragonal $\alpha\text{-(Mn,Fe)}_3\text{O}_4$, whereas for 20Fe, bixbyite phase is mainly transformed into cubic $\beta\text{-(Mn,Fe)}_3\text{O}_4$ and, in a minor extent, into the tetragonal spinel. In the case of oxidation reaction, both $(\text{Mn,Fe})_3\text{O}_4$ phases (cubic and tetragonal) are converted into bixbyite.

Finally, based on Raman spectroscopy, a reason for the improvement caused by Fe on the oxidation kinetics was suggested. Fe incorporation might alter the bond energies between divalent Mn cations and oxygen anions, facilitating its mobility through the lattice during the oxidation process. This eventually led to faster reactions with increasing Fe content.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

Experimental curves used for extraction of kinetic data; Influence of flow configuration, sample mass and gas flow on the oxidation reaction; XRD patterns of the synthesized 1Fe and 20Fe samples at 900 °C; Master Plot construction; Sestak-Berggren analyses of reduction and oxidation reactions; Evolution of E_a versus reaction extent for reduction and oxidation reactions; 1Fe vs 20Fe α -t plots; Master Plot for 1Fe oxidation reaction

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